

Structural and Biological Studies of Thiadiazole- Metal Complexes

HERJINDER KAUR^a and S. K. SANGAL^{*b}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, N. A. S. (P. G.) College, Meerut-250 001

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Meerut College, Meerut-250 001

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The 2,5-disubstituted-1,3,4-thiadiazole derivatives are known to exhibit a wide spectrum of pharmacological properties¹. Their complexes may be expected to display better biological activities due to presence of the -N-C-S moiety in these compounds². Keeping this in view, we report here synthesis, characterisation and biological screening of the first row transition metal complexes with 5-phenylamino-2-thio-(2',4',6'-trinitrophenyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (L).

Results and Discussion

The analytical results (Table 1) suggest 1 : 2 (M : L) stoichiometry for all the complexes except Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes. All the complexes are insoluble in common organic solvents but soluble in DMF and DMSO. The molar conductance values of the com-

plexes in DMF (10^{-3} M) at 25° in the range 6.5–15.5 Ω^{-1} cm² mol⁻¹, indicate their non-electrolytic nature.

IR spectra of the ligand exhibit medium intensity bands at 3 300 and 3 150 cm⁻¹ attributable to ν_{asy} and ν_{sy} NH stretches respectively. On complexation, these bands shift to lower region by 25–10 cm⁻¹ suggesting involvement of exocyclic N atom of NH group in coordination³. The medium intensity band at 710 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C ring)⁴ in free ligand shows a downward shift on complexation suggesting participation of ring sulphur in bonding with metal ions. The $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ (cyclic) band at 1 610 cm⁻¹ in the ligand remained practically unchanged in the complexes, indicating non-involvement of thiadiazole ring nitrogen atoms in bonding. The bands at 270–330 cm⁻¹ (M-S)⁵ are observed assigned to in all the complexes while $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ bands of

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd./ (M.p., °C)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				μ_{eff} B M.
	N	S	Cl	Metal	
[Mn(C ₁₄ H ₈ N ₆ O ₆ S ₂) ₂ (Cl) ₂] (270)	17.45 (17.39)	13.35 13.25	7.39 7.35	5.70 5.68)	5.80
[Fe(C ₁₄ H ₈ N ₆ O ₆ S ₂) ₂ (Cl) ₂] (300)	17.42 (17.37)	13.25 13.24	7.38 7.34	5.70 5.77)	5.60
[Ni(C ₁₄ H ₈ N ₆ O ₆ S ₂) ₂ (Cl) ₂] (290d)	17.45 (17.32)	13.25 13.20	7.28 7.32	6.09 6.05)	3.20
[Cu(C ₁₄ H ₈ N ₆ O ₆ S ₂) ₂ (Cl) ₂] (265d)	17.30 (17.24)	13.20 13.13	7.20 7.28	6.48 6.52)	1.85
[Zn(C ₁₄ H ₈ N ₆ O ₆ S ₂)(Cl) ₂] (260)	15.15 (15.09)	11.42 11.50	12.88 12.76	11.90 11.74)	-
[Cd(C ₁₄ H ₈ N ₆ O ₆ S ₂)(Cl) ₂] (260)	13.85 (13.92)	10.68 10.60	11.82 11.76	18.70 18.62)	-

amino group appeared at 410–475 cm^{-1} . The $\nu_{\text{M-Cl}}$ bands at 265–245 cm^{-1} in the Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes are in agreement for six-coordinate metal halide complexes⁶. The $\nu_{\text{M-Cl}}$ band at 265–245 cm^{-1} in the Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes are in agreement for six-coordinate metal halide complexes⁶, while these bands appeared at 235 and 220 cm^{-1} in the Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes.

Biological screening : The ligand and complexes were screened against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* by agar plate diffusion technique. The ligand, the Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes were found more active against *S. aureus* than *E. coli* (zone of inhibition 50, 45, 48 mm respectively). The Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes were moderately active (30–35 mm).

Fungicidal screening was evaluated against *D. tetramera*, *A. alternaria* and *F. oxysporum* by growth method. Toxicological data indicated greater fungicidal activity of the ligand (74.5–75.2% at 500 ppm) than the complexes (71.4–54.2% at 500 ppm).

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Complexes were analysed for metal, N and S by standard methods⁷. The physical measurements were also carried out by standard procedures. The ligand (L) was prepared as per literature⁸. The complexes were synthesised by refluxing (~1 h) ethanolic solutions of the ligand (0.01 mol; 20 ml) and the metal chlorides (0.01 mol; 15 ml). The Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes sepa-

rated immediately and addition of solid sodium acetate was necessary to facilitate the complexation in Ni^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes. In the preparation of Fe^{II} complex the solvents were thoroughly bubbled with nitrogen gas before mixing and the reaction mixture was refluxed under nitrogen atmosphere to prevent oxidation of metal ion. The separated complexes were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure over CaCl_2 .

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